

of southwestern Bangladesh were affected (see figure). In addition, farmers reported its occurrence in many other remote areas that we could not visit, making the total affected area much greater. The infection level for the rice crops was 10-100% with the boro crop being least affected under boro or boro-fallow patterns compared with transplanted aman - boro or transplanted aman - boro - transplanted aus patterns. Yield loss was estimated to range from 20 to 100% in transplanted aman and DWR, from 10 to 100% in boro rice, and from 10 to 50% in transplanted aus rice

(see table). Many fields had 100% crop loss, with the proportion higher in DWR and transplanted aman than in the boro crop.

Both local and modern rice varieties were susceptible to ufra disease.

Based on our observations and interviews with farmers, we identified several reasons for the spread of ufra disease in transplanted aman, boro, and transplanted aus rice: cultivating of the boro crop in DWR and transplanted aman fields previously infected with ufra, raising seedlings in infected fields, irrigating

seedbeds with water from infected fields, exposing fields to irrigation water from infected fields, planting infected seedlings in ufra-free areas, and selling infected seedlings.

To control this disease, farmers need to learn how to identify its symptoms early, the nature of its devastation and modes of survival and spread, and how to apply different control measures from the seedbed to the main fields. These measures will help to prevent the spread of the disease from endemic to ufra-free rainfed lowland and irrigated rice areas. ■

Effect of temperature and light on growth and sporulation of fusarium rice sheath rot

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The main causes of rice sheath rot (ShR) in Manipur, India, — *Fusarium moniliforme*, *F. graminearum*, and *F. avenaceum* (IMI 342486) — were isolated and maintained on potato

dextrose agar. We studied the effect of temperature and light on their growth and sporulation.

We aseptically cut 5-mm disks from actively growing pure cultures of ShR fungi and transferred each disk to a 100-ml Erlenmeyer flask containing 50 ml of potato dextrose broth. Sets of flasks were incubated in the dark at 5°, 10°, 15°, 20°, 25°, 30°, 35°, or 38 °C for 7 d. Other flasks were kept at 26-27°C during the day and 18-19°C during the night and exposed to 24 h of light (provided by cool white fluorescent tubes [6500 °K 20

W]), or 24 h of darkness, or 12 h of light and 12 h of darkness for 7 d. All treatments were replicated three times for growth and three times for sporulation studies. Growth of each culture was estimated on a dry-weight basis; number of spores/ml was calculated using a hemocytometer.

F. avenaceum produced the most growth at 25 °C and *F. moniliforme* and *F. graminearum* at 30 °C. None of the cultures grew at 5° or 38 °C. Maximum sporulation for the fungi was at 30 °C, although they did not sporulate at 5°, 10°, 15°, 35°, and 38 °C (Table 1).

F. avenaceum and *F. graminearum* grew best in complete darkness but *F. moniliforme* grew best in complete light. Alternate light and darkness inhibited growth (Table 2).

F. avenaceum and *F. graminearum* produced the most spores in complete darkness. Complete light markedly inhibited their spore production. Though *F. moniliforme* produced an appreciable quantity of spores in both complete light and complete darkness, alternate light and darkness had a synergistic effect on spore production (Table 2). ■

Table 1. Effect of temperature on growth (dry weight) and sporulation of fungi associated with ShR in darkness.

Temperature (°C)	<i>F. avenaceum</i>		<i>F. moniliforme</i>		<i>F. graminearum</i>	
	Growth (mg)	Spores/ml (no.)	Growth (mg)	Spores/ml (no.)	Growth (mg)	Spores/ml (no.)
5	0	0	0	0	0	0
10	110	0	98	0	88	0
15	140	0	110	0	97	0
20	205	4 × 10 ²	118	4 × 10 ³	121	4 × 10 ²
25	284	4 × 10 ³	212	16 × 10 ³	183	4 × 10 ³
30	213	8 × 10 ³	317	4 × 10 ⁴	310	4 × 10 ³
35	93	0	105	0	121	0
38	0	0	0	0	0	0
CD (0.05)	4.4		4.8		4.5	

Table 2. Effect of light on growth (dry weight) and sporulation of fungi associated with ShR.

Source of light ^a	Temperature (°C)		<i>F. avenaceum</i>		<i>F. moniliforme</i>		<i>F. graminearum</i>	
	Night	Day	Growth (mg)	Spores/ml (no.)	Growth (mg)	Spores/ml (no.)	Growth (mg)	Spores/ml (no.)
Complete light	18-19	26-27	257	1 × 10 ²	240	4 × 10 ³	319	2 × 10 ²
Complete darkness	18-19	26-27	328	3 × 10 ³	200	4 × 10 ³	345	6 × 10 ³
Alternate light (12 h) and darkness (12 h)	18-19	26-27	190	2 × 10 ²	210	8 × 10 ³	165	4 × 10 ²

^aCrompton cool white fluorescent (2-ft) tube with electric discharge of 6500 °K 20 W.